

(Revising the strong statement, an explanation of the chapter on hadith) تنقيح القول الحثيث شرح لباب الحديث

also known as "Tanqih al-Qaul bi Sharh lubab al-Hadith."

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Arabic, Text, Language, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions

The text was an explanation of a book written on the virtues and prohibition of certain practices in the light of the verse of the Qur'an and Traditions of the Prophet (SAW). The text was designed into forty chapters to establish the stronghold of some activities in Islam by presenting the activities' virtues to attract Muslims' attention towards their stronghold, such as virtues of Knowledge, Prayer, Charity, Supplication, repentance, and a host of others. On the other dimension, Warnings against some sinful acts were presented for people to keep away from them, such as Pornication, Drinking Alcohol, homosexuality, and the like. Sokoto caliphate had considered the book among the texts from which some principles of the state were derived for the people's mutual existence and stability.

Date Range: 1804 CE - 1903 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: جلال الدين السيوطي. تنقيح القول الحثيث شرح لباب الحديث. تنقيح القول الحثيث شرح لباب الحديث. دار إحياء كتب العربية. 2022.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://doc-10-2c-prod-03-apps-viewer.googleusercontent.com/viewer2/prod-03/pdf/9jn1e0jcb4vuhlg2rg91jrkel93775u/rn469s7etlipkjiinkaqb3j5ic4ovnv/1704206925000/3*/APznzabSF_xulaikGt1cOe9Lo9qLQj6Bg0atqxCcaWVcmtDJ1voatCV0Ldh5Cjip4IzVrACg98wj60NIm_1TICxefVgWC9XHSDpJnNrx18FSaWF-IF_qm2v74XydgO6619dOGHTJAQNILwtY9zeKITgfeVBL0xfPChTy3iIX7cjKwSldfuVLH5mXFhsIOgbRahfxcxf6Fd8vQ7TJiiZXc80OyI-TxJcB0rCqa-YXDAq-r0l03rcz3OCmeiTUyDJOnVMn_g5xplvNcId5FeLafepEK6zLp18Y0q2mpm17kAnK4sWcHIV7_k00PSk1XQfvGq1fR4LePfPrCI-J4bLrm62qEDP_mNigOyhOkN2n_M-02ZMqrCJw2WUStpVxbL8fg7Zi1JMw==?authuser

– Source 1 Description: المكتبة المفتوحة

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ketabonline.com/ar/books/67660/read?part=1&page=1&index=606633>

– Source 1 Description: جامع الكتب الإسلامية

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– without Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: White.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– No

Shrine

– No

Altar

– No

Devotional marker

– No

Cenotaph

– No

Church

– No

↳ Mosque
– Yes

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops
– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– Yes

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: Bookshop and Markets.

– Yes

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Bookshop and Markets.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present full-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present part-time?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - No

- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
– No
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
– No
- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?
– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?
– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– Total audience: 10000000
– Total audience: 10000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)
– Number: 5000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience
– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience
– largest audience: 8000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)
– Number: 5000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience
– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience
– largest audience: 8000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Nature of audience
[select all that apply]
– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?
– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

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↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

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↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Moral Ethics.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– No

↳ Exile?

– No

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

↳ Ostracism?

– No

↳ Seizure of property?
– No

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?
– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?
– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?
– No

Are formal burials present in the text?
– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?
– No

↳ In cemetery?
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Washing, Shrouding and funeral prayer to the dead body.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Creation of other beings.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

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 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Descend rainfall.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - Yes
 - Notes: Messengers and Prophets.
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - Yes
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Messengers and Prophets.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

– Yes

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Messengers and Prophets.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

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- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms
 - No
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 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
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 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Creation of the other beings.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- Yes
- Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
–Specify: Descend the Rainfall.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Yes
Notes: Messengers and Prophets.

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

– Yes

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Messengers and Prophets.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Communicate through other means
 - Specify: Mysterious.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Movement from one place to another.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings' punishment is under the directives of the High God.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - No
- ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: Burning in the Hellfire.

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings' punishment is under the directives of the High God.

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 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: Burning in the Hellfire.
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– No

↳ Other?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– No

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
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↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
– Yes

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↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– No

↳ Other?
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↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– Yes
- ↳ Other?
–Specify: General success in life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
– No

↳ At specified time in future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– No

↳ At some other time [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Only the High God knows the time.

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Paradise and Hellfire.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

- Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

- Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

- Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

- Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
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- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
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- ↳ Cooperation
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 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?
– Yes

- ↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 5

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 100

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 3

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A band

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?
– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?
– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?
– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?
– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?
– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?
– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?
– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?
– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: marriage.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed the virtues of legal warfare.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

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